

DEVELOPING RHYTHMIC PERCEPTION SKILLS IN STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: In this article, I emphasized the development of music perception skills in students with disabilities, supporting the development of creativity skills in the use of instruments and stimulating learning with improved quality, learning and shaping their thinking, learning and development.

Keywords: student with disabilities, inclusive education, Braille.

Under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, additional measures related to improving the education system were adopted based on the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020, "On additional measures to further improve the education system." The main goal is to create a safe inclusive learning environment for students, establishing conditions for their education.

In this regard, creating a safe inclusive learning environment for students is crucial. Additionally, developing tools to determine the quality and effectiveness of inclusive education, creating an "Inclusive Education" training module for improving the skills of teaching staff, and implementing it in practice are currently in progress.

Therefore, it is essential to learn what needs attention in creating a safe inclusive learning environment for students and to ensure that each student reaches an independent level according to their needs, allowing them to achieve a high level of inclusivity in the learning environment.

To achieve this, a single requirement is imposed on all teaching staff participating in the educational process. In this context, it is essential to provide all teaching staff with a comprehensive set of communicative techniques and skills in social relationships, which will contribute to preparing students for social life within the family, local community, and society in general.

Furthermore, specific requirements are set for general education school classrooms, both in general education schools as a whole and within each classroom. Since all general education schools are designed for the education of healthy children, it is necessary to provide special equipment, tools, textbooks, learning materials, and facilities for visually impaired, hearing impaired, physically weak, and weak-sighted children.

In addition to this, students with limited opportunities are provided with education based on general programs, and all teachers in general education schools are actively involved in the educational process. However, special education specialists (deaf educators, blind educators, oligophrenopedagogues) work as special education teachers in collaboration with teachers, especially for students with limited opportunities.

General education programs are developed and implemented based on individualized education programs designed for each direction (visual, auditory, cognitive). These individualized teaching programs are taught through individual guidance, using adapted educational materials and employing individualized teaching methods.

Moreover, students with limited opportunities may have different interests, despite their similar ages. Although the ages of students with limited opportunities may be the same, they differ from each other and have diverse thoughts and concerns.

Furthermore, the interest in music is a common trait among such students. However, it's not accurate to say that everyone is interested. Some students are reserved, while others, conversely, are cheerful. Some like to listen, while others, conversely, cannot express themselves well.

In addition, creating a positive emotional environment is crucial for rehabilitating students with limited opportunities, especially in situations where there may be sudden changes in social and personal conditions, leading to anxiety.

Likewise, some students may not be able to imitate sounds, hum tunes, or pronounce simple musical phrases. Finding a solution to this issue is the teacher's responsibility. While students with limited opportunities may not understand how to synchronize music with movements, and they may not be able to imitate movements even by listening or repeat them by watching, they still have imitation traits. This characteristic helps shape the imitation skill, facilitating the imitation of sounds and movements during singing, making the melodies clear.

In this case, the teacher is required to:

- Conduct diagnostics;
- Select a group of instruments that is suitable for the issues of students with limited opportunities;
- Allow students with limited opportunities to choose musical instruments from the group they prefer;

- Propose the selection and listening of musical pieces during the performance of each instrument;
- Identify a list of works performed by selected instruments chosen by students with limited opportunities;
- Concluding stage.

Achieving the goal through musical works involves the following stages:

- Diagnostics;
- Selection of musical works;
- Selection of concluding works.

As evident, it is possible to organize activities with students with limited opportunities using musical works and musical instruments, and shape the listening skills for their musical preferences.

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